

RESEARCH ARTICLE

From Homeland to Wordscape: Diasporic Testimonio in the Poetry of Mahmoud Darwish

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ABSTRACT

Darwish's literary output encompasses all shades of these themes, including alienation, marginalisation, despair, nostalgia, readjustment, assimilation, adaptation, and adoption. As a writer of Diasporic Testimonio, his writings are autobiographical. In his poems, he portrays a kind of cultural in-betweenness. The power structures marginalise these people. They are the natives of their own homeland, which is found in every protest literature where cross-fertilisation takes place. Mahmoud Darwish's poems are often preoccupied with the elements of nostalgia as he seeks to locate himself in a new culture. His poems depict the culture of his homeland, which was once beautiful, and at the same time, he also registers the painful agony of adapting to a new space that had become terrible. The Ghettoisation and discrimination of the displaced communities result in a sense of dismemberment and marginalisation in the host country. In the displacement, discontinuity, and fragmentation, the writers experience various cultural processes and ethnic mixtures within a multicultural setup, to which they are inevitably drawn. Through Mahmoud Darwish's works, it can be inferred that there is a hectic search for securing and establishing a new home in the country where they lived, and in this new home, they create an identity that is deeply rooted in the past, where power structures had silenced them.

Keywords: alienation; displacement; fragmentation; ghettoisation

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Mahmoud Darwish, a Palestinian, was born in the Galilee village of Al-Birwa, which the Israeli army conquered and subsequently destroyed. Darwish and his family were classified as internal refugees or present-absent aliens as they failed to appear on the official Israeli census. For a long time, Darwish was an expatriate residing in Paris and Beirut. For reasons including performing poems and unlawfully travelling between communities, Darwish spent time in prison in the 1960s. Some have called him the "resistance poet," and after his poem "Identity Card" became a protest song, he was put under house arrest. Darwish worked for the Cairo newspaper Al-Ahram after spending a year at the University of Moscow in 1970. After that, he settled in Beirut and served as editor of Palestinian Affairs for a decade, from 1973 to 1982. The Palestinian Liberation Organisation's executive committee included Darwish from 1987 until 1993. His return from exile to see loved ones in Palestine was authorised in 1996. The occupation of Mahmoud Darwish's native land is reflected in his early work from the 1960s and 1970s.

Located to the east of the Mediterranean Sea, Israel is the sole Jewish state in the world. The Arab population originally from the area that is now under Israeli rule calls it Palestine, and its current inhabitants desire to create a state using that name on all or some of the occupied land. The question of control and ownership of land is at the heart of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Although Jewish and Arab Muslim claims to the territory date back thousands of years, the present-day political struggle began in the early twentieth century. In an effort to escape persecution at home, persecuted Jews sought refuge in what was then Muslim- and Arab-majority Ottoman and British Empire territory. Because they believed the territory to be rightfully theirs, the Arabs fought back. After the failure of an early UN plan to divide the area, Israel and the neighbouring Arab nations fought multiple battles for the land. The modern lines are largely a result of the outcomes of two of these battles, the first of which took place in 1948 and the second in 1967.

Because it gave Israel control of the territories that were still inhabited by Palestinians—the West Bank and the Gaza Strip—the 1967 war is a pivotal event in the conflict. Despite Israeli rule, the West Bank was ostensibly under Palestinian administration. Israeli "settlers," a Jewish group that has steadily expanded its settlements in the West Bank, have essentially denied Palestinians access to their homeland. In contrast, Israeli forces have imposed Israeli security restrictions on Palestinian movement and activity. Despite being under Israeli embargo, but not

ground force occupation, the Islamist fundamentalist party Hamas now controls Gaza. For the first time since 2007, the two Palestinian factions may have united on April 23, forming a shared Palestinian government.

Israeli and Palestinian forces went to war in July and August 2014 after peace talks broke down. The most popular proposal for ending the Israeli-Palestinian issue is the "two-state solution," which would divide the land between Israel and Palestine. Under this plan, Israel would control the majority of the West Bank and Gaza, while Palestine would control the remaining territory. In theory, the two-state idea makes perfect sense, but in practice, the two camps remain sharply divided. A "one-state solution," in which the entire territory is absorbed by either Israel or Palestine, is an alternative to the two-state solution. Despite widespread pessimism about the potential benefits, this result is gaining momentum due to demographic and political factors. The Holocaust, which killed six million Jews during World War II, increased the number of Jews desiring independence. The Arabs who previously resided in Palestine and the neighbouring countries did not welcome the new nation because they felt it was unfairly handed a substantial portion of what they considered their traditional home. The conflict erupted in 1948. At its conclusion, Egypt controlled the Gaza Strip, and Jordan controlled the West Bank. Thousands of Palestinians who had fled from Israel, the new Jewish homeland, were contained in them. However, following yet another battle in 1967, Israeli forces occupied these Palestinian territories and remained for many years. The Israelis' greatest wish was that the Arab countries would acknowledge Israel's right to exist and put an end to the conflict in exchange for the territory they had captured. Despite Israel's 2005 withdrawal from Gaza, the territory was quickly taken over by a group known as Hamas following their electoral victory. A large portion of the global community views Hamas as a terrorist group. The 1.5 million Palestinians who call the Gaza Strip home had it tough. Israel has complete sovereignty over its coastline and all points of entry and exit. You can also enter Egypt at another crossing point. A functional airport does not exist. Restricted access makes it difficult for commodities to enter or exit the Gaza Strip. While food is legally permitted, humanitarian organisations have noticed a decline in the amount of meat and fresh produce consumed by households. Outages occurred. Businesses were unable to export many of their goods from Gaza, resulting in a high unemployment rate, while consumers had limited disposable income. Forcibly displaced or forcibly removed from their homes, hundreds of thousands of Palestinians sought sanctuary in neighbouring countries during the conflicts that broke out in 1948 and 1967. There were about 4.6 million Palestinian refugees and their descendants, with many residing in camps across Syria, Jordan, Lebanon, the West Bank, and the Gaza Strip. The UN

was able to provide them with assistance. Despite the lack of an army, rockets were frequently fired into Israel from Gaza by the Palestinians. Israelis residing in border communities would seek cover and adjust their lifestyles to cope with the rocket attacks. Several Israeli offensives have targeted Gaza since Israel's troop withdrawal in 2005. According to Israel, these were launched in an effort to halt the rocket attacks. Israeli forces invaded Gaza in 2008. Prior to the declaration of a ceasefire, thirteen Israeli troops and an estimated 1,300 civilians were killed in Gaza. An Israeli operation in 2012 resulted in the deaths of six Israelis and 167 Palestinians. After eight days of fighting, both sides agreed to halt their attacks and announced a ceasefire. During fifty days of violence, nearly 2,200 people were murdered (mostly Palestinians) and many more were injured, according to officials as of July 2014. On August 26th, Israel and Hamas reached an agreement to end hostilities.

In 1964, the Arab League sought to manage Palestinian nationalism by establishing the PLO, giving the impression that they were championing the cause. As a result of the Arab loss in 1967, the PLO was seized by more radical and youthful Palestinians, who were able to achieve partial independence from Arab rule. The PLO comprises a variety of political and armed factions, each with its own distinct ideology. The Chairman of the PLO from 1968 until his death in 2004 was Yasser Arafat. Fatah, the main PLO group, was also led by him. In addition to these two main factions, there are several smaller ones, including the PFLP, DFLP, and, within the Occupied Territories, the PPP (formerly the Communist Party of Palestine). Despite these factional disagreements, the majority of Palestinians saw the PLO as representing their interests until the Oslo Accords of 1993 and the foundation of the Palestinian Authority in 1994 caused it to lose importance to the Islamist group Hamas, which first emerged in the late 1980s. Even more so, the PLO's influence was eroded by the emergence of Hamas, particularly in the 2000s.

Jordan was the principal base of operations for the PLO in the late 1960s. The PLO's leadership was driven from Jordan in 1970 and 1971 due to conflict with the Jordanian army; they were then forced to relocate to Lebanon. In 1975, the PLO became involved in the Lebanese civil war. In 1982, following Israel's invasion of Lebanon, the PLO leadership was forced to leave the nation and return to Tunisia. Israel refused to recognise the Palestinian people as a sovereign nation or an equal combatant with Israel until 1993. Israel insisted on postponing negotiations with any Arab state other than the PLO since, in its view, the latter is nothing more than a terrorist organisation. It argued that Palestinians should be integrated into the current Arab states rather than given the option to form their own state. When Israeli officials

secretly met with PLO representatives, the impasse dissolved, and the Oslo Declaration of Principles was signed in 1993. Following Yitzhak Rabin's 1992 ascension to the prime ministership, human rights circumstances in the Gaza Strip and the West Bank worsened considerably. Many members of the Palestinian delegation resigned in protest of this turn of events, which cast doubt on their credibility during the talks in Washington.

In the West Bank, dozens of Palestinian villages near the "seam zone" staged popular resistance to oppose the barrier's segregation and the seizure of their farmland. To prevent bulldozers from digging the foundations of the barrier, villagers staged demonstrations and other forms of protest. To avoid being uprooted, they fastened themselves to olive trees, slashed the barrier in half where it was a fence, and sprayed graffiti on parts where it was a concrete wall. Thousands of Israelis, including members of the International Solidarity Movement and groups such as Ta'ayush/Palestinian-Israeli Partnership and Anarchists Against the Wall, have rallied in support of the Palestinian people's resistance and regularly participated in its events. Some of the land that had been taken for the construction of the separation barrier was returned during the four-month "peace camp" in the village of Masha in the spring and summer of 2003, as well as comparable initiatives in other communities. Even the poets of the region are considered a potential flashpoint in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Originally from what is now Israel, Mahmoud Darwish passed away in 2008. Darwish became famous in 1965, at the age of 24, with his poem "Identity Card." This is only one of several works in which he provided Palestinians, especially those residing in Israel, a platform never before seen. Darwish has the potential to be irate about Israel. He has also asserted that every Palestinian hamlet was the site of a pivotal event, such as the slaughter in Deir Yassin in 1948. Still, reducing Darwish to a terrorist is to misunderstand his ideas, his work, and his character. There was no violent streak in Darwish. In the midst of a violent confrontation, he was a rare breed of person who persisted in gauging the Other by their own characteristics; he was a humaniser.

Write down

I am an Arab

I have a name without a title

Patient in a country

Where people are enraged

My roots

We were entrenched before the birth of time

And before the opening of the eras

Before the pines, and the olive trees

And before the grass grew (IC 17-26)

In both his ideas and his poetry, Darwish delves deeply into history. From the words quoted above, it is clear that his poetry has a strong fixation on the past. An outstanding work of poetry, the aforementioned piece skillfully weaves together history, anthropology, sociology, geography, and psychology in many permutations. This intertextuality opens up possibilities for introspection and the re-creation of history, the latter of which contains the world's hidden reality. It is clear from Darwish that historical events, both personal and political, are remembered through the eyes of the individual. All the while, this endeavour places the past in a nostalgic and critical light with respect to the present. To further complicate matters, Identity Card places individual lives in the midst of political and historical events that seem to be at odds with one another. Multiple viewpoints on reality or truth emerge when two or more people recall and recount events from distinct personal vantage points, shaped by the manipulation of power structures for their own purposes. Although it seems loftier than philosophy, diasporic testimonio theory has limited literary criticism to analysing the surface level of art expressions. Theories such as those that deal with difference and deferral, otherness and Orientalism, politics and ideology, etc., have been present since the time of Homer and Plato, and critics and creative authors alike have continued to examine these issues. The principle differs solely in its preference to confine itself to the ideological and political, scornfully ignoring the moral and aesthetic concerns raised by literary works. This is in contrast to the early days of theory and literary criticism, which welcomed all forms of inquiry into literary works. Reviving literary criticism and reading, returning to a more comprehensive focus on issues, and ultimately elevating them to moral and aesthetic standards are all urgent needs. It must also be acknowledged that diasporic and testimonio literature is an art form, not journalism, politics, sociology, psychology, linguistics, or anthropology, but rather a synthesis of all these disciplines, all according to the rules of poetic truth and poetic beauty, as Arnold puts it. Diasporic testimonio thus gives Darwish's poetry the upper hand.

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